

Cadre management and the Chinese Pressure System

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ABSTRACT

The paper sheds new light on the rules and regulations that govern a cornerstone of the Chinese bureaucracy, the management of China's 50 million cadres. The paper focusses on cadre evaluation in the area of environmental protection and sustainable development and found that the CCP is moving towards evaluation templates based on quantifiable and measurable indicators. At the same time qualitative political evaluation criteria still apply. The combination of quantifiable and qualitative evaluation criteria has created intense pressure cascading downwards to the local level. The paper is based on primary data, e.g. official Chinese government outputs such as policy documents, speeches, and press releases as well as interviews with Chinese scholars and officials.

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